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Personal Space amongst Adolescents as a Function of Need Structure and Personal Traits

*Prof. (Dr.) Dinesh Kumar **

The present empirical study was conducted on 150 adolescents of Patna selected using purposive sampling technique. The purpose was to examine whether or not need structure dimensions (need for achievement, level of aspiration and risk-taking) and personal traits (self-concept, ego-strength and emotional maturity) influence personal space. It was hypothesized that : (i) Need structure dimensions would have significant association with maintenance of personal space; (ii) Personal traits would have significant influence on maintenance of personal space. For the purpose, Mukherjee Need for Achievement Scale, Singh's Level of Aspiration Scale, Choubey's Risk Taking Scale, Singh's SDPI and Singh and Bhargava's Emotional Maturity Scale were used to measure need for achievement, level of aspiration, risk-taking, self-concept, ego-strength and emotional maturity respectively. Besides these, PDS was used to seek the necessary information about the respondents. The personal space was measured experimentally. The obtained data were analysed using chi-square. It was found that respondents belonging to high need structure dimensions and high personal traits were found to maintain smaller personal space. Thus, it was concluded that maintenance of personal space is a function of need structure dimensions and personality traits under reference.

Introduction

The study under reference embodies some components which need elaboration. Need for achievement refers to strive for success or the attainment of the desired goal-Chaplin (1975), Reber et al. (2009) defined level of aspiration as the level of which a person aspires. It is the standard set by a person by which success or failure can be personally guessed. Risk taking is a hypothetical personality dimension reflecting to degree to which an individual willingly under takes actions that involve a significant degree of risk. Personality traits under study are self-concept, ego-strength emotional maturity. Self-concept refers to one's concept about oneself. A person with

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high self-concept are self-reliant and self-actualized (Reber et al. 2009), Ego-strength refers to the strength of people to tolerate anxiety and stress. A person with strong ego has capacity to tolerate anxiety and firm grip of reality. Contrary to it a person with weak ego are confused, un-adapting rigid, stereotyped and unoriginal - Chaplin (1975). Emotional Maturity is the next component which needs exploration. Actually, emotional maturity is not only effective determine of personality pattern but it also helps to control the growth of adolescent's development. The concept "Mature" emotional behaviour of any level is that which reflects the fruits of normal emotional development. A person who is able to keep his emotions under control, who is able to broke delay and to suffer without self-pity, might still. According to another author Seoul, if the emotional development of the individual is relatively complete, his adaptability his high, his regressive tendencies are low, and his vulnerability is minimal. Therefore the emotionally mature is not who necessarily has resolved all conditions that aroused anxiety and hostility but it is continuously in process of seeing himself in clearer perspective, continually involved in a struggle to gain healthy integration of feeling, thinking action.

Various personal factors like age, sex, education, familiarity etc. have deep impact on the preference of personal space (Dubey, 1967; Khan, 2007; Khan, 2004). Besides there are personality factors, cultural factors and situation factors affecting personal space. Folarin (1980) found that space preference varies with grade and sex of interacting pairs of children. McDowell (1972) tried to study behavioural manifestation at the violation of personal space. Several studies showing the effect of personal variables on personal space have been made. But there are dearth of Indian studies relating to the impact of ego-strength and modernity on personal space and hence the under taking of this study is justified. Studies reflect that personal space is a function of sex and modernity (Kumar et al. 2005), socio-familial correlates (Kumar and Singh, 2009), intra-familial factors (Kumar et al., 2011), mental health and life satisfaction (Kumar, D. 2011), sex-difference (Kumari, S. 2006) and several psychological factors (Kumar, 2011). Thus, we see that personal space has not been conducted in India especially in context of Bihar. There are some studies linked with need structure dimensions and factors other than personal space (Chaubey et al., 1974; Krishna, 1972; Krishna, et al., 1975; Kumari, 2004; Supriya, 2002; Frank, 1935; Tariayl et al. 1973). This justies undertaking of the present study.

Purpose

The present study has been undertaken with the objectives to compare personal space among adolescents in context of (i) need structure dimensions and (ii) personal traits. (iii) Further, it was intended to examine the relationship among the variables.

Hypotheses

Keeping in view the objectives of the present study, the following hypotheses were formulated for empirical verification :

- (1) Need structure (need for achievement, level of aspiration and risk taking) dimensions will significantly influence the maintenance of personal space among the respondents.
- (2) Personality traits (self-concept, ego-strength and emotional maturity) will significantly influence the maintenance of personal space among the respondents.
- (3) There will be significant relationship among the variables under study.

Method of Study

Sample Used

The study was conducted on a sample consisting of 150 male adolescents of Patna based on purposive sampling technique. They were matched in respect of SES, Inhabitation and other familial conditions.

Research Tools Used

- A PDS was used to get the other necessary information about the respondents.
- Mukherjee's Sentence Completion Test was used for measuring the need for achievement of adolescent respondents.
- Aspiration Level Scale by Singh, A.K. was used for measuring aspiration level of the respondents.
- Chaubey's Risk-taking Scale was used for measuring risk-taking of the respondents.
- SDPI was used to measure self-concept and ego-strength of the respondents.
- Emotional Maturity Scale by Singh and Bhargava was used to measure the emotional maturity of the respondents.
- Personal space was measured experimentally.

Procedure of Data Collection

Scales along with PDS were employed on the respondents and data were obtained. Thereafter they were divided into high and low groups in respect of need for achievement, level of aspiration, risk taking, self-concept, ego-strength and emotional maturity using

the respective median as cuts. The respondents in a small group were asked to sit in a hall comfortably. Thereafter, the distance of respondent from the researcher is measured which is called personal space between respondents and researcher. In this way personal space of each respondent were measured.

Data Analysis : The collected data were analysed and treated with the help of chi-square and the obtained results were interpreted aptly.

Results and Interpretations

Table - 01

Chi-square showing influence of need structure dimensions on maintenance of personal space amongst adolescents.

Need Structure Dimensions	Gr.	N	Personal Space		χ^2	df	P
			Large	Small			
Need for Achievement	High	90	30% (N=27)	70% (N=63)	29.17	1	<.01
	Low	60	68% (N=41)	32% (N=18)			
Level of Aspiration	High	88	31% (N=27)	69% (N=61)	24.75	1	<.01
	Low	62	66% (N=41)	34% (N=21)			
Risk-taking	High	87	30% (N=26)	70%(N=61)	26.18	1	<.01
	Low	63	66% (N=42)	34% (N=21)			

The results displayed by table-01 clearly revealed the fact that more than 70% (N=63) of high need for achievement group maintained smaller personal space whereas only 30% (N=27) of this group maintained larger personal space. Similarly more than 68% (N=41) of low need for achievement group maintained larger personal space and only 32% (N=18) of this group maintained smaller personal space. The chi-square was found significant ($\chi^2 = 29.17$; df = 1; p<.01).

Further, more than 69% (N=61) of high level of aspiration group maintained smaller personal space whereas only 31% (N=27) of this group maintained larger personal space. Similarly more than 66% (N=41) of low level of aspiration group maintained larger personal space and only 34% (N=21) of this group maintained smaller personal space. The chi-square was found significant ($\chi^2 = 24.75$; df = 1; p<.01).

Finally, 70% (N=61) of high risk-taking group maintained smaller personal space whereas only 30% (N=26) of this group maintained larger personal space. Similarly more than 66% (N=42)

of low risk-taking group maintained larger personal space and only 34% (N=21) of this group maintained smaller personal space. The chi-square was found significant ($\chi^2 = 26.18$; $df = 1$; $p < .01$). Thus hypothesis no. (1) is retained. The findings might be interpreted on the ground that person with high need structure dimensions are self-confident and are less likely to be influenced by negative forces like anxiety and stress leading to maintain smaller personal space.

Table - 02

Chi-square showing the influence of self-concept, ego-strength and emotional maturity on personal space amongst adolescents.

Variables	Groups	N	Personal Space		χ^2	df	P
			Large	Small			
Self-concept	High	86	28% (N=24)	72% (N=62)	30.73	1	<.01
	Low	64	67% (N=43)	33% (N=21)			
Ego-strength	High	88	28% (N=25)	72% (N=63)	33.96	1	<.01
	Low	62	69% (N=43)	31% (N=19)			
Emotional Maturity	High	89	32% (N=28)	68% (N=61)	27.65	1	<.01
	Low	61	69% (N=42)	31% (N=19)			

The results displayed by table-02 clearly revealed the fact that more than 72% (N=62) of high self-concept group maintained smaller personal space whereas only 28% (N=24) of this group maintained larger personal space. Similarly, more than 67% (N=43) of low self-concept group maintained larger personal space and only 33% (N=21) of this group maintained smaller personal space. The chi-square was found significant ($\chi^2 = 30.73$; $df = 1$; $p < .01$).

Further, more than 72% (N=63) of high ego-strength group maintained smaller personal space whereas only 28% (N=25) of this group maintained larger personal space. Similarly, more than 69% (N=43) of low ego-strength group maintained larger personal space and only 31% (N=19) of this group maintained smaller personal space. The chi-square was found significant ($\chi^2 = 33.96$; $df = 1$; $p < .01$).

Finally, more than 68% (N=61) of high emotional maturity group maintained smaller personal space whereas only 32% (N=28) of this group maintained larger personal space. Similarly, more than 69% (N=42) of low emotional maturity group maintained larger personal space and only 31% (N=19) of this group maintained

smaller personal space. The chi-square was found significant ($\chi^2 = 27.65$; $df = 1$; $p < .01$). Thus hypothesis no. (2) is fully retained. This finding might be interpreted on the ground that person having high personal traits are full of confidence leading to have sound interaction without hasitation and maintenance & smaller personal space.

Conclusions : (1) Personal space is a function of need structure dimensions. The high need for achievement, high level of aspiration, high risk-taking all are condusive to maintenance of smaller personal space.

(2) High personal traits namely high self-concept, high ego-strength and high emotional maturity all are liable to maintain smaller personal space.

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